

CULTiVATE

Food Sharing in Athens

Impact report

Jennifer Lyons & Anna Davies

November 2025

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, REA or UKRI. Neither the European Union nor the granting authorities can be held responsible for them.

Overview

37 Food sharing initiatives mapped in Athens

29 Initiatives include redistributing food, saving surplus food from disposal and providing food for those in need

10 Initiatives include cooking and eating together, strengthening social connection and improving nutrition

13 Initiatives include growing food, reducing food costs for participants and for supporting physical and mental wellbeing

14 Initiatives undertake more than one activity around food, contributing to a more circular bioeconomy

Annual estimated FSI impacts in Athens from 37 FSIs*

Social **92,722** meals shared

Economic **31** tonnes of food produced

Civic engagement **1,184** volunteers active

Environmental **65,732** tonnes CO₂e avoided

**Impacts estimated using The Toolshed SIA and the CULTIVATE Food Sharing Map.*

Executive Summary

Food Sharing Initiatives (FSIs) support people to grow, cook, eat, and redistribute food together, as well as share knowledge and spaces. They can contribute significantly to more sustainable, resilient, and socially connected urban food systems. Athens has an emerging food sharing landscape shown below:

FSIs geolocated in Athens (2025)

This report presents estimated sustainability impact scenarios for Athens, combining a snapshot of results from the automated mapping of FSIs in Athens using CULTIVATE's Food Sharing Mapping tool with data from sustainability impact assessments conducted by FSIs. Scenarios provide low, medium and high estimates of sustainability impact at the city scale.

How to use this report

This report can be used to help support transitions to more sustainable food systems in Athens. This includes using the report:

- **As an evidence base:** Use these scenarios as a baseline from which to track and monitor FSI sustainability impacts over time.
- **For policy evaluation:** Identify where FSI activities currently take place and where there are gaps in provision to ensure municipal and national food, climate and community goals are met.
- **For goal tracking:** Map contributions from FSIs to the global sustainable development goals and to local food and food waste targets.

Food sharing in Athens

Using CULTIVATE's automated Food Sharing Map, FSIs with a digital presence (web, app, social media) were identified and categorised by activity type: Growing; Cooking & Eating; Redistribution; Multifunctional (e.g. engaging in more than one activity). In Athens, FSIs concentrate most heavily in the central urban core, particularly in and around the historic centre and adjacent dense districts. This clustering aligns with areas where population density and social diversity are highest, and is a typical pattern found in other European cities.

Some FSIs extend east and southeast of the centre, in neighbourhoods with mixed residential and commercial uses, with many undertaking redistribution activities. A number of initiatives appear towards the northern periphery, where additional space may support storage, logistics, or small growing sites. However, growing initiatives do appear in quite central areas, suggesting that even though available space is more constrained, small-scale or community-oriented urban growing models operate.

By contrast, the western part of the metropolitan area displays very few visible FSIs. This suggests the potential influence of industrial land-use patterns, limited digital visibility of local actors, or fewer community-based food initiatives operating with an online or map-identifiable presence.

Mapping of FSIs is the first phase of the SIA calculation process, which is set out below.

City-scale impact estimation

Impacts were calculated using a four-step process:

1. **Map** – Identifying FSIs and classifying them according to their activity type.
2. **Calculate** – Estimating a) the mean average impact estimation per indicator category b) the low impact estimation and c) the high impact estimation, using SIA data from all forms of FSIs across nine European cities, as follows:
 - Growing – tonnes of food produced
 - Cooking and eating – number of meals shared
 - Redistribution – Tonnes of CO₂e avoided
 - All FSIs – Number of volunteers engaged
3. **Scale** – Multiplying the number of FSIs in each activity category by the a) mean average b) lowest and c) highest impact figure from CULTIVATE FSI SIA impact data to generate city-level estimates.
4. **Scenarios** – Illustrating the range of possible outcomes in municipal food sharing activity.

Athens impact scenarios

The table below presents the mean, low and high sustainability impact assessment scenarios for Athens.

Food sharing activity	Adjusted No. of FSIs	CULTIVATE average impact per FSI	Mean Impact Scenario Athens	Low Impact Scenario Athens	High Impact Scenario Athens	Metric
Growing	n.4.66	4	31	10	244	Tonnes food produced
Cooking & Eating	n.7.66	13,908	92,722	333	598,666	Meals shared
Redistribution	n.25.66	2,561	65,732	3,285	410,667	Tonnes CO ₂ e avoided
All FSIs	n.37	32	1,184	722	4,181	Volunteers

These results provide an early indication of the scale of FSI impacts across Athens from 37 FSIs that have a digital trace. Expanding reporting practices within existing FSIs would create a broader picture of the sustainability impacts that the FSIs are creating beyond the narrow quantitative categories detailed in the table above. Research shows that FSIs [create impact across a range of social, economic, environmental and governance areas](#) contributing to urban sustainability, food waste reduction, and community resilience. Other FSIs may not have a digital profile or may not have a profile that the mapping tool can access, so do not currently appear on the map. These can be manually added if indicated and verified.

Recommendations

FSIs in Athens play a vital role in advancing urban sustainability through food for those who can access them. They save and share surplus food, build community, and enhance resilience. Even with preliminary mapping data and limited impact data points from 37 FSIs, their contributions are clear, measurable and meaningful.

Recommendations are to:

1. **Embed data collection** – Use mapping and SIA data to inform policy making. Strengthening data collection will help inform effective, inclusive urban food policy.
2. **Strengthen the FSI ecosystem** – Use data on the distribution of FSIs and compare with the needs of populations to identify areas where FSIs should be supported. Use SIA data to evidence how FSIs can support unmet needs.
3. **Resilience planning** – Integrate FSIs into local food, health, and emergency planning frameworks.
4. **Food waste reduction** - Demonstrate urban-scale contributions to EU food-waste targets from FSIs to track progress toward 30% waste-reduction goals.

If you would like to know more about the method and data underpinning this SIA report, or if you would like to contribute to expanding the food sharing map contact us at: info@sharingsolutions.eu